

ISic3429

I.Sicily inscription 3429

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

sarcophagus;

tabula ansata

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2007.03.11

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

found in area to west of Corso Gelone, where palazzo built immediately south of Hotel Jolly

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Area archeologica della Neapolis, Orecchio di Dionisio e Teatro

Greco

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644824

Bibliography

Gentili, G.V. 1961. Nuovi elementi di epigrafia siracusana. *Archivio Storico Siracusano*. 7: 5-25. At 23-24 no.2 dr

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